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Implementing telemedicine for cancer care in European healthcare organizations: lessons from the eCAN Joint Action

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Conflicts of Interest

None declared.

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Abstract

Purpose: Telemedicine represents a promising innovation to complement conventional cancer care in Europe to improve treatment quality and patient outcomes. Funded between September 2022 and December 2024, the Joint Action ‘Strengthening eHealth including telemedicine and remote monitoring for health care systems for CANcer prevention and care’ (eCAN JA) aimed to bring the benefits of telemedicine to cancer patients across the European Union (EU) Member States, with 35 partner organizations from 16 countries and explored its feasibility through multicenter clinical trials. This study sheds light on key factors to implement telemedicine services for cancer care in European healthcare organizations (HCOs) and offers a forward-looking perspective by conducting a foresight exercise as part of the Sustainability Work Package (WP4) of the eCAN JA.

Approach: Foresight is an umbrella term for innovative strategic planning, policy formulation and solution design methods that empower decision-makers. For our multi-country foresight study, we followed three sequential steps to gain qualitative and quantitative findings on the facilitators of telemedicine services for cancer patients in clinical settings, comprised of (1) literature review; (2) surveys to HCOs in different EU Member States and (3) a foresight workshop with survey respondents.

Findings: Telemedicine implementation in HCOs requires equipping healthcare professionals with the necessary skills, ensuring system compatibility and addressing resource constraints for hybrid care models for success. Future policies in the EU should focus on establishing telemedicine training for healthcare professionals and support interoperability as well as user-friendliness of telemedicine services in HCOs. Policies should also address clinical workload challenges, enable harmonized telemedicine protocols across Europe, provide incentives for implementation, and invest in digital infrastructure in HCOs for a sustainable telemedicine adoption.

Originality: To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to conduct a foresight analysis on the feasibility of telemedicine for cancer care across different HCOs in EU Member States.

Keywords

Foresight, European Union, Telemedicine, Health service delivery, Cancer care

1 Purpose

Cancer remains one of the most significant causes of mortality in Europe. Indeed, Europe's cancer burden in 2020 included 4 million new cancer cases and close to 2 million deaths in one year, indicating on average 11,000 new cases and 5,000 deaths every day (Dyba *et al.*, 2021). This burden is compounded by substantial discrepancies in timely cancer detection and survival rates, driven by inequalities in preventive measures, access to advanced diagnostic tools, treatment options, and quality of care both between and within European countries (Berchet *et al.*, 2023; Leclercq *et al.*, 2024). The rise of telemedicine offers a new way to address healthcare challenges, as most notably demonstrated during the Covid-19 pandemic (Azambuja *et al.*, 2020; Gottlob *et al.*, 2025). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), telemedicine employs digital technologies to bridge geographical gaps in healthcare delivery, offering opportunities to enhance clinical management and broaden service accessibility (WHO, 2022). Defined as digitally enabled remote care, telemedicine can therefore act as a useful tool to complement traditional, in-person health services by improving cancer care quality and patient outcomes, especially when travel barriers lead to delayed screenings, diagnoses, and treatments (Baldwin-Medsker *et al.*, 2020; Børøsund *et al.*, 2020; Burton *et al.*, 2022). Implemented well, telemedicine can even result in cost savings in health systems without compromising quality of life or care (Qaderi *et al.*, 2021).

Funded between September 2022 and December 2024, the Joint Action 'Strengthening eHealth including telemedicine and remote monitoring for health care systems for CANcer prevention and care' (eCAN JA) aimed to bring the benefits of telemedicine to cancer patients across the European Union (EU) Member States, especially for those living in remote and rural areas (eCAN JA, 2022). Involving 16 countries and 35 key partners, including ministries, national public health institutes, universities, hospitals, and cancer centers across the EU, this project explored the feasibility of telemedicine in cancer care and conducted multicenter clinical trials among diverse populations of cancer patients (European Commission, 2023). Aiming ultimately to increase the quality of life of cancer patients, the main objectives of the eCAN JA were to (1) enhance telemedicine for cancer care by prioritizing quality and meeting the expectations of end-users; (2) improve the preparedness of healthcare professionals, particularly in situations where the isolation of cancer patients is needed or when patients reside in remote regions; and (3) facilitate capacity building and foster the development of compatible telemedicine solutions in Europe. The multicenter clinical trials of the eCAN JA ran in 18 healthcare organizations (HCOs) across 10 EU Member States.

As observed in the multicenter clinical trials of the eCAN JA and noted in earlier studies as well, implementing telemedicine for cancer care in HCOs, such as hospitals and comprehensive cancer centers, is not necessarily a straight-forward process (Ftouni *et al.*, 2022; Kane *et al.*, 2022). Healthcare professionals may remain hesitant to adopt digital technologies in clinical settings, despite

reimbursement being available and patient willingness to use these services (Farmaki *et al.*, 2025). Clinicians may, for instance, experience changes in their daily responsibilities due to telemedicine, and they could be held liable for malpractice without proper regulation on remote care (Parimbelli *et al.*, 2018). Understanding the usual clinical workflow, setting clear rules for the adoption, addressing the critical human factors for implementation, and recognizing the critical physician-patient relationship are thus some examples for key steps in the successful design and development of telemedicine (Wang and Byrd, 2017; Sánchez-Polo *et al.*, 2019; Cegarra-Sánchez *et al.*, 2020; Garavand *et al.*, 2023). Given the increasing interest in telemedicine services across Europe and the crucial role that healthcare professionals play in this field, we aim to understand in this study the facilitating factors to implement telemedicine in clinical oncology in the EU and gain a forward-looking perspective by conducting a foresight exercise as part of the Sustainability Work Package (WP4) of the eCAN JA. In doing so, we specifically focus on meso-level (organizational) factors, examining the conditions within HCOs that enable the successful implementation and scaling of telemedicine services.

2 Methodology

Foresight is an umbrella term for innovative strategic planning, policy formulation and solution design methods that empower decision-makers (UNDP, 2018). For our study, we followed three sequential steps to apply a foresight methodology that yielded both qualitative and quantitative results, using an explanatory sequential design (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2018). Between June 2023 and August 2023, a rapid literature review was conducted, which provided main facilitating factors for the use of telemedicine services in HCOs (meso-level implementation). These factors served as a basis for the survey that was sent to the experts who work for the meso-level implementation of telemedicine services in different EU Member States. They represented mainly healthcare professionals working in clinical cancer centers and university hospitals. The online survey was open only to the invited experts between September 2023 and December 2023. Following the closure of the survey, a foresight workshop was organized in February 2024 to understand their reasoning, gain qualitative insights in addition to the quantitative survey results, and discuss the future of telemedicine implementation in clinical oncology in the EU. Below, we explain the methodology of these three steps in detail.

2.1 Literature review methodology

A rapid literature review was conducted from June 2023 to August 2023 to identify facilitators for the implementation of telemedicine services in HCOs by using PubMed and Cochrane library. The main inclusion criteria were studies in peer-reviewed journals published (1) with a focus on telemedicine solutions aimed at cancer patients; (2) as review papers such as scoping review, systematic

reviews, and meta-reviews; (3) between 2020 and June 2023; and (4) in English language. The EU Member States were of primary interest when selecting the studies given that the aim of the foresight exercise was to suggest actions to improve the implementation of telemedicine in cancer care in European HCOs. However, systematic review studies for the rapid literature review were based on existing primary literature from different countries; it was therefore not possible to focus exclusively on published studies originating from Europe. Both the abstract and full-text screening were conducted independently by two co-authors of this study and conflicting outcomes were discussed until finding an agreement.

2.2 Survey methodology

Based on the content analysis of the literature review, the lead author of this study formulated the questions for an online survey. Before the dissemination of the survey, it was piloted by two other co-authors of this study and one experienced clinician working on cancer care in a university hospital. Where necessary, the wording of the survey questions was changed based on their feedback, while still adhering to the core findings of the literature review. The survey included 26 potentially facilitating factors to be evaluated on a 4-point Likert scale to yield quantitative outcomes. The 4-point Likert scale was chosen to capture varying degrees of perceived enabling potential of factors for telemedicine implementation in HCOs (neutral, rather enabler, enabler, strong enabler). The online survey was conducted via LimeSurvey between September 2023 until December 2023, open only to the invited experts who work in the telemedicine implementation at the organizational level for healthcare provision, most of whom were affiliated with the eCAN JA multicenter clinical trials across different European countries. The survey results were presented to the WP leads of the eCAN JA, including but not limited to information technology (IT) professionals, physicians, and stakeholder engagement experts, in a face-to-face meeting in Brussels on 21 February 2024. The aim of this meeting was the validation of the interpretation of survey results and future scenarios to discuss with the survey respondents during the foresight workshop.

2.3 Foresight workshop methodology

To gather qualitative outcomes, all experts representing HCOs who had filled in the survey were invited to a foresight workshop. The presentation of the survey results was sent to the experts representing HCOs in advance who confirmed their availability, including the questions to be addressed during the workshop. Experts could, therefore, collect additional information before the meeting to better prepare for the discussion. Besides collecting their generic comments on the current situation on telemedicine services in their settings, the following four hypothetical scenarios were illustrated to the

experts to facilitate the discussion during the workshop and understand their positioning on the implementation of telemedicine services in HCOs:

- i. An enabling policy environment and high openness of patients to use telemedicine services
- ii. A discouraging policy environment but high openness of patients to use telemedicine services
- iii. An enabling policy environment but low openness of patients to use telemedicine services
- iv. A discouraging policy environment and low openness of patients to use telemedicine services

The workshop took place on 29 February 2024 and the expert discussion was facilitated by the lead author of this study. The process of consensus-building among the experts was iterative: After the workshop, the same foresight scenarios were recirculated among all survey respondents to collect additional feedback and increase the number of expert contributions. Statements from both the workshop and the written responses were transcribed and analyzed qualitatively. More specifically, the content was thematically structured around three key phases—preparation, implementation, and scaling up—to inform the development of phase-specific recommendations for navigating future scenarios. The draft recommendations were then sent back to the experts for validation of the interpretations. Their feedback was used to refine the final recommendations, which were subsequently recirculated to all participants for transparency and confirmation.

3 Findings

3.1 Outcomes of the literature review

After the content analysis of the 21 included studies, 26 key factors were identified that potentially ease the implementation of telemedicine services for cancer care in European healthcare settings. PRISMA flow diagram of the rapid literature review is shown in Figure 1, and Supplementary Material presents the included studies and their content analysis.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram of the review process (Source: Authors' own work)

3.2 Outcomes of the survey

A total of 24 experts participated in the survey. Of these, 22 were from 12 EU Member States. In addition, two experts from a European umbrella organization for health service delivery provided insights at the EU-level, resulting in the following structure: Belgium (1), Cyprus (2), Denmark (2), Greece (2), Hungary (1), Ireland (4), Italy (1), Lithuania (3), Poland (1), Portugal (2), Slovenia (1), Spain (2) and EU-level (2). Except for the European umbrella organization and the institutions from Denmark and Poland, all survey respondents were from the eCAN JA multicenter clinical trials. The country distribution of the respondents is illustrated in Figure 2. As Table 1 demonstrates, most of the experts work at clinical cancer centers and (university) hospitals. Table 2 gives an overview of the responses of the participating experts.

Figure 2. Country distribution of the survey respondents, highlighted in blue (Source: Authors' own work)

Table 1. Participants of the study (Source: Authors' own work)

Survey respondents	Country	Number
Clinical cancer center	Cyprus, Italy, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal	6
University hospital	Belgium, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Spain	6
Hospital	Greece, Lithuania	3
Comprehensive cancer center	Hungary, Slovenia	2
National health service authority	Ireland	2
Regional health service authority	Denmark, Spain	2
European umbrella organization for health service delivery	EU-level	2
Cancer organization providing supportive care	Cyprus	1
		<i>Total: 24</i>
Foresight workshop participants (among the survey respondents)	Country	Number
Comprehensive cancer center	Hungary, Slovenia	2
Clinical cancer center	Lithuania	1
University hospital	Ireland	1
Hospital	Greece	1
European umbrella organization for health service delivery	EU-level	1
		<i>Total: 6</i>

Table 2. Survey results for influential factors driving telemedicine forward in healthcare organizations (Source: Authors' own work)

	Neutral	Rather enabler	Enabler	Strong enabler
1. Digital literacy of the physicians (i.e. their digital competency and technical capability to navigate through telemedicine services)	1	1	11	11
2. Digital health literacy of the patients (i.e. their digital health competency and technical capability to navigate through telemedicine services)	1	5	8	10
3. Openness of physicians to the implementation of new technologies, hence telemedicine services, in healthcare organizations	0	1	11	12
4. The availability of qualified (trained) staff to implement telemedicine services in healthcare organizations	1	2	11	10
5. The overall satisfaction of patients with telemedicine services	1	2	12	9
6. A smooth integration of telemedicine services into the existing clinical workflow	0	2	12	10
7. A sense of assurance that the implementation of telemedicine services will not increase the workload for physicians	3	2	8	11
8. A strong managerial support at a higher level for prioritizing the use of telemedicine services in the healthcare organization	1	5	12	6
9. The existence of guidelines/protocols on how to use the telemedicine services (reducing the uncertainty about healthcare professionals' roles, what is expected from them, which patient groups are relevant, when to follow up, etc.)	2	5	11	6
10. A user-centered design of telemedicine services that are convenient to use	0	3	10	11
11. The possibility of providing seamless (i.e. integrated and person-centered) care with telemedicine services	1	5	10	8
12. The availability of tailored telemedicine services, based on the specific needs of patient groups	1	2	12	9
13. The motivation to keep patients safe from infectious diseases, for instance, during the Covid-19 pandemic	3	7	6	8
14. The presence of clear regulations that address medical liability issues associated with telemedicine services	2	6	12	4
15. A sense of assurance that the quality of the physician-patient relationship would not be diminished by telemedicine services	1	4	11	8
16. The potential of telemedicine services to provide more comprehensive patient data than conventional (in-person) consultations	4	5	9	6
17. A smooth integration of telemedicine services into the existing IT infrastructure, i.e. their interoperability	2	2	8	12

	Neutral	Rather enabler	Enabler	Strong enabler
18. The existence of sufficient IT infrastructure to make use of telemedicine services (e.g. having access to the internet and computer)	0	3	9	12
19. A high-quality of hardware/software relevant to telemedicine services (e.g. camera, microphone and other equipment)	2	5	9	8
20. A sense of assurance that the software for telemedicine services complies with the data protection, security and privacy rules	1	3	9	11
21. The availability of adequate IT support and maintenance of the telemedicine system	2	1	11	10
22. The availability of sufficient time, financial and human resources for a successful implementation of telemedicine services	1	1	7	15
23. The financial coverage of all the necessary equipment and hardware that are associated with telemedicine services (IT systems, telemonitoring devices, wearables, video systems, and software licenses)	1	1	9	13
24. An identical reimbursement rate of telemedicine services as in-person consultations (i.e. no financial discrepancy between telemedicine and conventional services)	4	4	8	8
25. The intention to create a positive spill-over effect (i.e. synergies) with other ongoing digital services that are being implemented in the healthcare organization	4	5	11	4
26. The intention to use time more effectively in terms of mitigating "no-shows" (i.e. patients who do not appear despite existing appointments)	4	6	8	6

3.3 Outcomes of the foresight workshop

All survey respondents (in total 24) were invited to an interactive foresight workshop to understand their reasoning about the survey responses and collect qualitative data based a discussion on four hypothetical scenarios in the future. Among the invited experts, six of them (25%) were available to comment on the scenarios. These six participants stemmed from five EU Member States and one European umbrella organization: Greece (1), Hungary (1), Ireland (1), Lithuania (1), Slovenia (1) and EU-level (1). The organizational distribution of the workshop participants is shown in Table 1. Below, we present the qualitative outcomes gained from the discussion during the workshop.

Greece, statements from a hospital

In a scenario where both policy support and patient openness align, the foundation for telemedicine implementation is strong, yet challenges such as technological accessibility in hospitals and clinician training remain significant. The participant emphasizes the importance of clinicians being adept at using telemedicine platforms, not just for direct patient interaction but also for the exchange of various patient documents. Moreover, the importance of patient safety in telemedicine is underscored, with a call for clear protocols for emergency situations.

In environments where patient openness is high despite a discouraging policy environment, the participant suggests leveraging this openness through information campaigns and interest groups aimed at both policymakers and healthcare professionals. The idea would be to showcase the tangible benefits of telemedicine, informed by pilot projects and patient feedback, to foster a shift in policy attitudes.

Where policy support exists but patient openness is lacking, the focus should shift towards making telemedicine more engaging and accessible. Strategies should include enhancing the user-friendliness of telemedicine platforms and providing support for those less comfortable with technology or those without the latest digital tools. Encouraging trials of telemedicine services to allow patients first-hand experience and providing them the choice between digital and in-person consultation could be viable solutions.

In the most challenging scenario of both discouraging policy environments and low patient openness, a tailored approach that considers the specific needs and cultural contexts of different communities is advocated. This should involve engaging patients in the design of tele-counseling programs and combining strategies from previous scenarios to simultaneously address policy barriers and patient hesitancy.

Hungary, statements from a comprehensive cancer center

The current policy environment in Hungary is not seen as discouraging to the use of telemedicine, and there is generally high openness among patients towards these services. The National eHealth Infrastructure (EESZT) serves as a cloud-based platform in the country, connecting general practitioners (GPs), specialist care, pharmacies, and the public. It consolidates a wide array of healthcare data, including the medical history of patients, vaccinations, examinations, surgeries, blood tests and prescriptions, into a central platform accessible to both patients and healthcare providers. This comprehensive system fosters positive experiences with digital health solutions, enhancing public trust in telemedicine and electronic data storage services.

However, challenges arise due to inadequate IT facilities at some healthcare institutions, which hinder the full utilization of digital services. The primary concern of the participant relates to technical limitations within healthcare settings, which affect the seamless delivery and use of telemedicine services. These limitations point to a need for upgrading technical infrastructure to ensure the widespread and effective use of telemedicine across the country. Moreover, some patients face socio-economic barriers that impede their access to telemedicine services: Issues such as old mobile phones that are incompatible with desired innovative services highlight the digital divide.

Ireland, statements from a university hospital

According to the expert, the adoption of telemedicine in the rural regions of Ireland presents a promising solution to alleviate the burden on the healthcare system and reduce the need for lengthy travel for cancer patients. However, challenges in HCOs such as technological barriers, including significant firewall issues and cybersecurity concerns, complicate its implementation. The necessity of finding a General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant technological tool, acceptable to both patients and the healthcare system, underscores the need for a harmonized approach across Europe. In addition, healthcare professionals should be sufficiently trained: Especially nurses' preference for in-person patient interactions highlights a reluctance to transition to remote care, despite the potential of visual telemedicine interactions to improve existing communications via telephone.

In terms of inclusivity, the lower survival rates and lack of regular follow-up appointments for cancer patients with intellectual disabilities indicate a critical area for telemedicine. The specific challenges faced by this group, such as higher anxiety levels and a general reluctance to attend hospital appointments, point towards the need for tailored services. Providing specialized telemedicine services for them would be especially beneficial and could improve their outcomes. Lastly, although favorable, 24-hour telemedicine service access require evidence-base at the health system level, including resource allocation and the need to justify such services through cost-benefit analysis.

Lithuania, statements from a clinical cancer center

The key hurdle identified by the expert is the lack of IT knowledge among physicians, particularly those of the older generation. This gap in digital literacy, coupled with the significant costs associated with renewing and maintaining IT infrastructure in HCOs, suggests a need for targeted IT education for healthcare providers and investments. After the Covid-19 pandemic, where legal frameworks have been adapted to facilitate telemedicine in HCOs, the challenge remains in making these digital health services appealing to patients. The expert underlines the importance of IT security and the necessity for regular software updates and modern hardware, and advocates for starting IT education very early, ideally at the school level. This foundational approach to digital literacy, both among patients and physicians, is seen as critical to overcoming barriers to telemedicine adoption.

Slovenia, statements from a comprehensive cancer center

The expert reflects a supportive stance towards digitalization in healthcare from both the government and the population, particularly the younger generation. Despite this support, practical challenges such as heavy workloads in hospitals and a high patient volume hinder swift telemedicine implementation. Most cancer patients prefer in-person consultations for physical examinations and necessary checks like blood tests. However, once these initial steps are completed and clinical results are obtained, telemedicine may become an attractive option for follow-up consultations, offering convenience and efficiency for both patients and healthcare providers.

EU-level, statements from a European umbrella organization

The expert emphasizes the importance of digital health literacy among cancer patients, acknowledging the geographical and logistical barriers that residents face in accessing healthcare services in Europe. The existence of medical deserts in Europe for cancer care is highlighted not just in rural but also in urban settings, underscoring the need for inclusive digital health strategies. Additionally, the potential of telemedicine to bridge language barriers is pointed out by offering services in the patient's native language, thereby enhancing the accessibility and personalization of healthcare. Telemedicine may be presented as a solution for patients who are physically unable to visit healthcare facilities due to geographical isolation or lack of public transport, as well as offering flexibility for those who might need to cancel in-person appointments due to last-minute issues.

Main recommendations are shown in Box 1.

Box 1. Recommendations to prepare, implement and scale up telemedicine services for cancer care in European healthcare organizations

Preparation

- Integrate IT education into school curricula to build technical knowledge and cybersecurity awareness from an early age
- Address the gap in digital literacy among healthcare professionals through dedicated courses, with a focus on accommodating the needs of the older generation
- Develop strategies to align the enthusiasm for digital health technologies among healthcare professionals with supportive policy and administrative frameworks
- Ensure that healthcare professionals are thoroughly trained and familiar with telemedicine platforms to facilitate the exchange of documents and handle emergencies adeptly
- Address hospital workload challenges before the actual implementation of telemedicine
- Invest in upgrading the IT facilities of HCOs to overcome structural limitations and ensure the efficient delivery of telemedicine services
- Develop telemedicine platforms with interactive interfaces to provide more engaging and personal experiences for patients
- Identify GDPR-compliant telemedicine platforms that meet the security and accessibility needs of patients and healthcare providers
- Learn from countries that have been widely using telemedicine to reduce inequalities in access to healthcare services

Implementation

- Implement initiatives aimed at reducing socio-economic barriers to telemedicine use, such as providing subsidies for modern telecommunication devices for patients or offering them accessible digital health training programs
- Consider different digital health literacy levels of patients to ensure everyone can benefit from telemedicine services
- Implement specialized telemedicine services for particularly disadvantaged individuals, e.g. those with intellectual disabilities, aiming to enhance care delivery within vulnerable population groups
- Ensure first-in-person examinations for cancer patients and offer telemedicine rather for follow-up consultations or rehabilitation services
- Offer trial periods for telemedicine services, allowing patients to choose between digital and in-person care after experiencing the benefits first-hand
- Test telemedicine among healthcare professionals to complement traditional telephone communications, particularly for nursing staff
- Secure investment for the regular renewal and maintenance of IT infrastructure in HCOs to support the demands of modern telemedicine services

Scaling up

- Organize information campaigns to improve the value and adoption of telemedicine services
- Consider the potential of 24-hour telemedicine access, including conducting cost-benefit analysis to support policy changes
- Harmonize telemedicine protocols across Europe, to include both top-down mandates to ensure consistency and compliance within healthcare systems and bottom-up approach to implementation
- Offer telemedicine services in multiple languages to cater to patients with different linguistic needs, ensuring inclusivity in cross-border healthcare

4 Discussion

As part of the Sustainability WP (WP4) of the eCAN JA, this study examined the facilitating factors to implement telemedicine services for cancer patients in European HCOs. Among the responses of the conducted survey, in particular the following factors stand out as facilitators for healthcare professionals: the availability of sufficient time, financial and human resources for a successful implementation of telemedicine services; the financial coverage of all the necessary equipment and hardware that are associated with telemedicine services (IT systems, telemonitoring devices, wearables, video systems, and software licenses); openness of physicians to the implementation of new technologies, hence telemedicine services, in HCOs; a smooth integration of telemedicine services into the existing IT infrastructure, i.e. their interoperability; and the existence of sufficient IT infrastructure to make use of telemedicine services, e.g. having access to the internet and computer (see Q22, Q23, Q3, Q17 and Q18 in Table 2 respectively).

In addition, the results of the foresight workshop reveal that healthcare professionals prefer to receive trainings on telemedicine before the actual use, emphasizing the importance of user-friendly and interoperable platforms. Trial periods for healthcare professionals and patients should offer first-hand experience to them, while harmonizing telemedicine protocols across Europe should ensure consistency. In addition, our results suggest that promoting digital literacy among patients and healthcare professionals facilitate the adoption of digital health technologies. These strategies, coupled with information campaigns for patients, can pave the way for telemedicine services.

A closer look at the three stages (preparation, implementation, scaling up) may provide some more tangible actions for telemedicine deployment. To start with, it is recommended to integrate IT knowledge into educational curricula early on and offer dedicated digital health trainings to healthcare providers. Moreover, proactively addressing clinical workload and upgrading technical infrastructure in HCOs should facilitate telemedicine implementation. These telemedicine platforms should be user-friendly and GDPR-compliant to engage end-users and ensure security, drawing lessons from countries where telemedicine has successfully reduced healthcare access disparities. Mitigating socio-economic barriers requires targeted interventions, such as providing subsidized devices and offering digital health literacy training. Indeed, accounting for patients' varying digital literacy should ensure telemedicine accessibility for all, with specialized services targeting disadvantaged groups to improve their care outcomes. It is, however, advisable that cancer care begins with in-person consultations, with telemedicine introduced gradually for follow-up or rehabilitation purposes, depending on individual needs and clinical appropriateness.

The existing initiatives in European countries should take into account some key factors for the sustainable scale-up of telemedicine services. Providing 24-hour telemedicine access could be

meaningful to implement; however, its economic implications should be assessed to inform large-scale policy changes. Especially in the context of EU cross-border care, harmonizing telemedicine protocols across Europe will be crucial, combining top-down mandates for consistency within Europe health systems with a bottom-up approach to proper implementation in HCOs. Given the linguistic diversity in Europe, offering telemedicine services in multiple languages could facilitate cross-border care and better accommodate patients who require translation assistance. Last but not least, our results highlight that the responsibility for implementing those recommended actions does not solely rest with the HCOs; rather, regulatory agencies should play a leading role.

Examining the broader literature on the use of telemedicine in HCOs, our findings seem to be in line with other peer-reviewed publications. Remote care gained particular attention during Covid-19 pandemic; hence several studies were published on telemedicine in recent years. A systematic review on the challenges of the use of telemedicine during the pandemic highlighted the importance of physician-patient relationship and stated major barriers in the HCOs such as IT-related aspects; privacy, data confidentiality and reimbursement of telemedicine services; and training of healthcare providers and patients on the use of telemedicine (Ftouni *et al.*, 2022). Another scoping review focusing on the attitudes of the GPs in Europe when using telemedicine supports this finding by stating that trainings and investments in digital infrastructure are inevitable during the preparatory phase of the implementation. Once the barriers are overcome and healthcare providers become familiar with telemedicine, they might be in favor of continuing virtual (cancer) care delivery for higher satisfaction of patients with healthcare services (Kjeldsted *et al.*, 2021; Turner *et al.*, 2022; Walley *et al.*, 2024).

Compared to the use of telemedicine in other diseases, one point stands out as the peculiarity of cancer care. Whereas, for instance, patients who suffer from mental health issues may feel more comfortable with remote care for the first contact and use telemedicine also for the continuation of their therapy, in-person visits to HCOs are crucial for cancer patients due to the nature of their disease, especially during the detection of the tumor (Kane *et al.*, 2022; Qaderi *et al.*, 2021; Walley *et al.*, 2024). Traditionally, cancer patients have benefitted from medical care, diagnostics, supportive care, and clinical trials in a centralized way, and offering decentralized telemedicine services to optimize cancer care pathways may require substantial financial investments in HCOs and geographically underserved areas (Lama *et al.*, 2022; Lloyd and Lee, 2022). Our study supports the existing evidence that using telemedicine for the post-surgery and post-cancer therapy follow-up may be more suitable for cancer patients and could enhance the acceptance of these services (Naik *et al.*, 2022). The face-to-face interactions and subtle non-verbal cues cannot be fully captured in remote care, especially during challenging discussions with seriously ill patients such as cancer (Worster and Swartz, 2017).

Notably, while telemedicine can improve cancer care, it may also reinforce existing inequities. Literature shows that access to telemedicine services is influenced by socioeconomic status, device and

internet availability, and language, whereas the use of these services is shaped by education, digital literacy, social support, age and comorbidities (Leclercq *et al.*, 2024). Addressing variations in digital literacy—not only among patients but also healthcare providers—has been identified by other researchers, as well as in our study, as one of the most viable strategies for the routine implementation of telemedicine (Knudsen *et al.*, 2021). In addition, equity among end-users of digital health innovations should be considered across the following dimensions: place of residence; race, ethnicity, culture, language, and religion; education and occupation; gender and sex; socioeconomic status; age; disability or complex needs; and marginalized group status (WHO/Europe, 2022). EU Member States need to develop context-sensitive, long-term implementation strategies to integrate telemedicine into routine cancer care and create policies that foster innovation for better health while addressing potential risks (Leclercq *et al.*, 2025; Saigí-Rubió *et al.*, 2022; Schmitt *et al.*, 2024; Turner *et al.*, 2022).

Admittedly, our study is subject to limitations. Firstly, the inclusion criteria confined the rapid literature review to studies in certain databases potentially omitted other relevant publications, causing a publication bias. Moreover, the survey and workshop methodologies, while meticulously designed, depended on the responses and engagement of invited experts, which might have introduced a selection bias. In this context, it should be noted that the majority of the study participants were from the eCAN JA multicenter clinical trials, indicating their high willingness to implement telemedicine practices in their clinical settings. Furthermore, the hypothetical scenarios used in the foresight workshop to guide discussions might not have captured the full complexity of real-world environments. Lastly, relying on expert feedback to finalize recommendations might not have fully illustrated the diverse viewpoints of HCOs across the EU. Future research with a larger and more stratified sample across EU Member States could support the development of a generalizable implementation framework.

Nonetheless, our study may help identify some key areas for improvement in telemedicine practices in European HCOs. With this foresight study, we applied a novel methodology to telemedicine implementation in cancer care, with a particular focus on organizational enablers. Our approach has been explicitly forward-looking and policy-oriented, aimed at supporting strategic decision-making in clinical implementation. Although the Covid-19 pandemic accelerated the uptake of telemedicine across the world, our findings extend beyond the crisis response, offering long-term relevance for digital transformation in cancer services. We deliberately focused mostly on structural challenges in clinical settings, with less consideration of the psychological and cultural dimensions of innovation deployment in HCOs. Future studies can build on our findings related to organizational aspects and connect them with rich qualitative insights from the behavioral sciences (e.g. how healthcare professionals may show resistance to digital technologies, adapt workflows, and transfer tacit knowledge within new environments). By incorporating cross-border dimensions and aligning with EU digital health priorities, our study contributes to broader policy efforts toward enhanced coordination across EU Member States.

5 Conclusions

As part of the eCAN Joint Action (2022–2024), the Sustainability WP (WP4) conducted a multi-country foresight study among different HCOs in the EU Member States. Telemedicine implementation in HCOs requires equipping healthcare professionals with the necessary skills, ensuring system compatibility, and addressing resource constraints for hybrid care models for success. Above all, infrastructural and financial support should be provided to HCOs for the integration of telemedicine services into the daily workflows of healthcare professionals. Future policies in the EU should focus on establishing a common telemedicine training for healthcare professionals and support interoperability as well as user-friendliness of telemedicine services in European HCOs. Policies should also address clinical workload challenges, enable harmonized protocols for telemedicine, provide incentives for implementation, and invest in digital infrastructure in HCOs for a sustainable telemedicine adoption in Europe.

The supplementary material for this article can be found online.

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